

Differences in total cholesterol and triglyceride levels between the trained and untrained groups after 30 minutes of running

Diferencias en los niveles de colesterol total y triglicéridos entre los grupos entrenados y no entrenados después de 30 minutos de correr

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Abstract

Increased levels of cholesterol and triglycerides can be caused by a lack of physical activity, resulting in plaque buildup in blood vessels and metabolic disorders. This study aims to explain the effect of total cholesterol and triglyceride levels before and after a 30-minute aerobic run carried out 4 times a week for 6 weeks on trained football players and an untrained group. This research method uses a quasi-experimental non-control group design that has been determined for the criteria as a research sample. The research sample used a purposive sampling method by taking 15 trained football players and 15 untrained people. Total cholesterol and triglyceride levels were measured before the 30-minute program and after the 30-minute program. The Shapiro-Wilk test showed a normal distribution. Data were analyzed using paired t-tests. The mean total cholesterol level before 188.06 ± 43.46 and after 158.86 ± 31.12 . The results of the data analysis showed that there was a significant effect on total cholesterol levels ($p=0.000$). For the level of triglycerides, the Shapiro-Wilk test showed a normal distribution. The result of the data analysis with Paired t-test showed there was no significant difference between the total triglyceride values of the two groups ($p=0.32$).

Keywords: cholesterol, triglycerides, exercise, trained, untrained

Resumen

Los niveles elevados de colesterol y triglicéridos pueden deberse a la falta de actividad física, lo que provoca acumulación de placa en los vasos sanguíneos y trastornos metabólicos. Este estudio tiene como objetivo explicar el efecto de los niveles de colesterol total y triglicéridos antes y después de una carrera aeróbica de 30 minutos realizada 4 veces por semana durante 6 semanas en jugadores de fútbol entrenados y un grupo no entrenado. Este método de investigación utiliza un diseño de grupo sin control cuasiexperimental que se ha determinado para los criterios como muestra de investigación. La muestra de la investigación utilizó un método de muestreo intencional al tomar a 15 jugadores de fútbol entrenados y 15 personas no entrenadas. Los niveles de colesterol total y triglicéridos se midieron antes del programa de 30 minutos y después del programa de 30 minutos. La prueba de Shapiro-Wilk mostró una distribución normal. Los datos se analizaron mediante pruebas t pareadas. El nivel medio de colesterol total antes $188,06 \pm 43,46$ y después $158,86 \pm 31,12$. Los resultados del análisis de los datos mostraron que hubo un efecto significativo sobre los niveles de colesterol total ($p=0,000$). Para el nivel de triglicéridos la prueba de Shapiro-Wilk mostró una distribución normal. El resultado del análisis de datos con la prueba t pareada mostró que no hubo dife-

rencias significativas entre los valores de triglicéridos totales de los dos grupos ($p=0,32$).

Palabras clave: colesterol, triglicéridos, ejercicio, entrenado, no entrenado

Hyperlipidemia is increased blood fat levels due to increased lipid peroxidation by free radicals. Total cholesterol levels in the body are said to be increased if the levels are >200 mg/dl and triglycerides >150 mg/dl. In Indonesia, data from the National Basic Health Research (RISKESDAS) in 2018 showed that 28.8% of people aged >15 years had abnormal cholesterol levels^{1,2}. Increased cholesterol and triglyceride levels can be caused by a lack of physical activity, resulting in plaque buildup in the blood vessels and metabolic disturbances. Reducing cholesterol and triglyceride levels can be helped by regular and significant aerobic exercise. Based on previous research, running for 12 minutes regularly for about 4 times a week can reduce cholesterol by 200 kcal/day²⁻⁴. Based on the World Health Organization (WHO) and research in the United States on physical activity guidelines that are recommended to the public by spending at least 75 minutes or 150 minutes a week to exercise, in approximately one day you can do running for 10-20 minutes⁵.

Physical activity resulting from skeletal muscle contraction will result in energy expenditure from within the body. Lack of physical activity can affect the decrease in the number of triglycerides. Exercise is repetitive body movement to improve the quality of physical fitness and reduce the risk of developing coronary heart disease⁶. Exercise is claimed to be able to reduce triglyceride levels because free fatty acids are used by muscles as a source of energy. People with a lack of physical activity have a higher triglyceride level which increases the risk of heart disease⁷.

Football is a sport that combines aerobic and anaerobic because in football it takes running so almost 70% is aerobic. In this study, running for 30 minutes was chosen because that time covered the recommended time and did not take too long for individuals to do. Running can increase 5-10% levels of High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL) and increase the use of fat as an energy source thereby reducing the accumulation of Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) and triglyceride levels^{2,8}. Based on Huldani's research, running 30 minutes can change and improve the physiological efficiency of the body, especially the immune system, such as temporary changes (responses), and permanent changes, and can increase the number of blood neutrophils³.

It was found that young athletes participating in regular training experienced increases in total antioxidant capacity, ascorbic acid, uric acid, α -tocopherol levels, superoxide dismutase activity, and significant increases in HDL-c levels in response to oxidative stress induced by physical activity, especially aerobics⁹. Increased ROS and decreased antioxidant defense systems can also cause stress after exercise. However, this is not reflected in the triglyceride levels. It is known that senescent organisms are more susceptible to oxidative stress during exercise due to age-related, ultrastructural, and biochemical changes that facilitate the formation of ROS. Furthermore, muscle repair and regeneration capacities diminish with old age, potentially increasing cellular oxidative damage¹⁰. The main defense reactions against ROS generation during exercise are superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase. These enzymes increase in response to exercise in vitro and in vivo studies¹¹⁻¹⁴. Marzatico et al reported that oxidant stress can develop during exercise, and increases antioxidant capacity in athletes with high physical activity¹⁵. Through this research, the triglyceride and cholesterol levels will be measured in trained football players and untrained groups after 30 minutes of running.

Researchers used a quasi-experimental model non-control group design to look for the effect of changes in total cholesterol and triglyceride levels before and after running 30 minutes 4 times a week for 6 weeks in trained football players and untrained groups.

Table 1. The mean of total cholesterol levels

No	Groups	Mean \pm SD Scoring
1	Untrained group	188.06 \pm 43.46
2	Trained football players' group	158.86 \pm 31.12

Table 1 shows that the average total cholesterol level after running 30 minutes in the football player group is lower than the non-football group. The results of measuring total cholesterol levels in the football player group were tested for normality using Shapiro-Wilk. The normality test results for total cholesterol levels in the football player group before the program and running 30 minutes were normally distributed (sig.=0.291). The normality test results for total cholesterol levels in the football player group after running 30 minutes were nor-

mally distributed (sig.=0.781). The normally distributed data was followed by paired t-test data analysis. The results of the paired t-test showed a value of $p = 0.00$ (<0.05) which means that the total cholesterol level after running 30 minutes was significantly different between the two groups.

Table 2. The mean triglyceride levels

No	Groups	Mean \pm SD Scoring
1	Untrained group	17.00 \pm 6.28 mg/dL
2	Trained football player group	19.47 \pm 6.32mg/dL

Table 2 shows that the difference in the number of triglycerides in the football player group is higher when compared to the non-football player group. The results of measuring the triglyceride levels in the football player group were tested for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk. The results of the normality test of the Shapiro-Wilk number of triglycerides in the football player group before running 30 minutes and in the football player group after running 30 minutes $p > 0.05$ shows that the data is normally distributed. Data that were normally distributed were followed by paired t-test data analysis with a 95% confidence level. Paired t-test results show a value of $p = 0.32$, showing no significant difference between the groups. The football player group showed a decrease in triglyceride levels with a difference of 8.23 mg/dl. The average number of triglycerides in the non-football group before running was 84 mg/dl and the average number of triglycerides after running was 83.53 mg/dl. The non-football group showed a decrease in the triglyceride level by a difference of 0.47 mg/dl.

some soccer players can be reduced by running for 30 minutes with regular exercise and sufficient frequency.

According to this study, regular and repeated exercise can reduce lipase enzymes in the liver, thereby inhibiting LDL catabolism and increasing HDL levels in the blood. Physical activity can increase lecithin cholesterol acyltransferase (LCAT) activity which will convert HDL3 cholesterol to HDL2 cholesterol and activate the pathway of reverse cholesterol transport. Another benefit of physical exercise is that it can reduce the activity of cholesteryl ester transfer protein (CETP), which reduces the rate of transfer of cholesterol from HDL to LDL or VLDL, thus increasing HDL performance. This study used gymnastics performed by Family Welfare Program members to see a decrease in total cholesterol in the body. Fatimah stated that physical activity has an inverse relationship with total cholesterol levels. The more strenuous the physical activity is, the lower the total cholesterol level¹⁷. In this study it was stated that the formation of ATP increases, thus making the body compensate by forming High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL) by providing access to excess cholesterol to the periphery which can be transported to the liver as an energy reserve. The results of this study were different from Inzana's study which stated that physical activity did not have a significant effect on cholesterol levels¹⁸. Physical activity performed on the elderly was not very effective in lowering cholesterol levels, there were several influencing factors such as lipid abnormalities in the body. Reduced metabolic activity in the body, especially in fat metabolism with age. The effect of metabolic disease on the elderly provides a decrease in cholesterol synthesis and a decrease in cholesterol absorption in the body, increasing total cholesterol levels.

Aerobic exercise can have an effect on reducing total cholesterol levels, and dyslipidemia as described in Mann's review. Exercise can increase some risks of cardiovascular disease and dyslipidemia. In this study, it was stated that the recommended exercise is an aerobic exercise with moderate-heavy intensity because it is faster in burning metabolism in the body, and the recommended exercise intensity is 20-40 minutes a week in 4-8 weeks to get significant results. This study took a combination of aerobic and anaerobic sports as explained in Steeve Mann's research that combination sports increase effectiveness in reducing lipid levels⁸.

This research shows that there was a decrease in the number of triglycerides in the football player group and the non-football group after running. According to Wang et al's research, a decrease in the number of triglycerides after exercise is associated with a decrease in Apolipoprotein C3 (apoC3). The research stated that after exercising there was a decrease in apoC3, apoC3 is a protein produced by the small intestine and liver which functions to inhibit activity. Lipoprotein lipase (LPL). Lipoprotein lipase is a protein that hydrolyzes triglycerides into fatty acids and glycerol so that high LPL activity can

Discussion

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that running exercise 30 minutes every 4 weeks for 6 weeks affects total cholesterol levels. Research that is in line is Lilazi's research which explains that physical activity in the morning exercise 60 minutes/per week for 3 weeks can reduce the total cholesterol levels of Family Welfare Program members^{15,16}. Several risk factors related to cholesterol levels are divided into two: risk factors that cannot be changed such as age, gender, and genetics. Modifiable risk factors such as diet and physical activity. The decrease in total cholesterol levels can be affected by physical activity by producing ATP. The more ATP formation in the body, the less total cholesterol formation. Running for 30 minutes can increase the concentration of oxygen in the blood and can improve blood flow so that cholesterol levels which initially tend to be high for

reduce the amount of blood triglycerides. It can be concluded that the lower the apoC3, the higher the amount of LPL which causes more triglycerides to be hydrolyzed and lowers the blood triglyceride level^{19,20}.

The results of the paired t-test showed a value of $p = 0.32$ which indicated that there was no significant difference between groups. This research is also consistent with the research of Chytra et al. that showed there was no statistically significant decrease in the number of triglycerides after four weeks of *poco-poco* exercise. This is because *poco-poco* exercise is only a low-intensity sport so it does not have an impact on blood cholesterol levels^{21,22}. In the results of research conducted by Othman et al stated that there was a significant decrease in triglyceride levels in 20 men after 8 weeks of a routine run at a moderate intensity. In this study, the decrease occurred significantly because the researchers measured the triglyceride levels after the research subjects routinely did jogging for 8 weeks, while the intensity of the exercise carried out by this research's subjects was moderate²³. The results of the normality test of the Shapiro-Wilk for total triglycerides in the football players and non-football players $p > 0.05$ showed that the data were normally distributed. Normal data continued at the 95% confidence level in unpaired t-test data analysis. Unpaired t-test results showed a value of $p = 0.868$, indicating no significant difference between groups.

The results of statistical analysis in this study showed that there was no significant difference in triglyceride levels of trained football players before and after running. The results of the analysis of this study also showed that there was no significant difference in triglyceride levels between groups of untrained football players before and after running. Likewise with the results of the analysis of triglyceride differences in football players and no insignificant results were obtained. This is because several factors can affect blood triglyceride levels, including food intake, alcohol consumption, smoking, gender, genetics, age, and exercise intensity. In this research, researchers have controlled for several factors such as taking research subjects who do not smoke and consume alcohol, and the research subjects were male between 16 and 22 years. In this study, the researchers did not control the food intake of the research subjects, and in this study did not measure the intensity of the exercise being carried out^{23,24}. This research also showed results that the average triglyceride level in the football player group was 80.60, and the average number of triglycerides in the non-football group was 83.76. This research showed that the total triglycerides in the football player group were lower compared to the non-football group, but statistical analysis showed there was no significant difference between the two groups.

Labovic et al. showed the same result that the average number of triglycerides among 30 athletes is lower than among 30 non-athletes and there is no significant difference in triglyceride levels between the two groups.

The lower number of triglycerides in the athlete group occurs because regular exercise can cause an increase in Lipoprotein Lipase (LPL). An increase in LPL can lead to an increase in triglyceride hydrolysis. In addition, this research also states that sports that are routinely performed by athletes can reduce lipogenesis activity. According to the findings of this study, running for 30 minutes can lower blood triglyceride levels, which means that running for 30 minutes can help prevent several diseases, including coronary heart disease. Since the reduction in triglycerides in this study was not statistically significant, further research is needed.

Conclusions

Based on this research can be concluded that running exercises for 30 minutes 4 times a week for 6 weeks showed a significant difference in the amount of cholesterol in both trained and untrained groups, but there was no significant difference in the triglyceride levels between the two groups. Further research is needed. The triglyceride levels should be measured while jogging for several weeks, along with the intensity of the exercise

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Conflicts of Interest

All authors have no conflict of interest, There is no conflict of interest to declare including financial and non-financial relationships.

Ethical Approval

Ethical Clearance No. 533/KEPK-FK/ULM/EC/XI/2022

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